

Universal Social Security in India!

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma

Email:drkrishnakantsharma@gmail.com; M; 9504782781

Abstract: In this article I have tried to put forward the significance and concern for a universal social security. Mere a financial arrangement never guarantee social security, especially in a country like India, which has tremendous depth of its social institutions, customs, traditions, and practices. While protesting those social institutions and practices it needed to appropriately fund individual in a manner that not harm the productivity of the country. Securing social security is a global concern now and these issues also required to take care off. It also needed to avoid any conflict in emerging social security institutions and existing one in order to making a swift transformation across the board. Therefore, it needed to work on all the three layers such as social equality, digitalization, and social security vendors. Social security vendors are important because it is a drive started by them amidst international development and globalist's ideas. One of the major issues would be in the future that it would be needed to see in the context of GST, Labor Reforms, and Financing so that it may be sustained properly. The success of ADHAR, Jan Dhan Scheme, and Digital India would need to go hand in hand as well the manner they get would orient in the future with respect to regulations. The social, political, economic, and technological perspectives needed to be properly defined and addressed. Even the social security fund management by the fund managers should be taken care off as it cannot not be expensive.

Keywords: Social Inequality in India; Causes of Social Inequality; Challenges of Social Inequality; Equal Compensation: Equal Distribution of Resources.

Introduction

The secular and modern ideas of the *social welfare, security, and protection* so far did not corroborate perfectly with the Indian society. No any social scheme would be successful without the support of the respective societies. A substantial data gap and lack of information persisted in terms of social security needs of different social groups. Without understanding their needs, it would be not appropriate to compensate them adequately. The respective roles of society, market, financial institutions, industries, and the government needed to be expedited. The project is expected to come out with strategies and approaches needed to implement and sustain any universal social security in India. The scattered social security arrangement in India needed integration and some patch up work would not be enough. The government has still not opted for a total non-contributory social security in India. There are various concerns at the moment, mainly related to the funds availability and allocation, or whether such scheme would be sustained or may adversely affect the productivity. Moreover, the social security in a modern democratic and welfare state cannot be separated from issues such as good governance, equality, and justice. In addition, the social security needed to go well with the social systems, problems, and objectives. Therefore, it is needed to understand and redefine the social security issues in terms of equality, democracy, and modernization, and globalization, social division of labour, productivity, and international development.

Different social groups in India have been faced with different problems and they needed different remedies. Therefore, the issues of universality may contradict with the issues of uniformity. There are many modalities of social security ranging from cash or kind benefits or ensuring any remedial action. Ensuring a spontaneous response is the need of the hour. The one of the dangers in the universal social security with uniformity would be of adequacy because the assistance provided may ultimately remain insufficient or may become redundant due to inflation or certain spatial or temporal factors. The social security needs of individuals or particular social groups needed to be evaluated.

The government has created several large structures that are not associated with the respective social problems and objectives. The Even such large structure is very rigid, permanent and highly bureaucratic. The government promoted social inequality through its policies of benefitting in a selective and exclusive manner. In this situation the universal social security would appear favourable, however, still a large inequality would persist between the respective formal and informal sector or among the people included or excluded. It may be required at some point of time to remove the existing distinctions between the formal and informal sectors.

The *Jan Dhan* and other bank accounts being linked to *Adhar*, would make direct benefit transfer quite convenient. The government's earlier plan to extend social security by creating employment opportunities and also creating national assets had not succeeded because of corruption, bad planning, and implementation of *MNREGA*. However, it would be still early to predict that any direct cash transfer of social security funds to the bank accounts of the respective beneficiaries would also promote productivity and create national assets.

The internet search and catalogues of various libraries also justified the gap of literature. There were swift changes in the formal social security also due to international development and globalization. The manner banks and new financial institutions operated and managed certain social security programs would demand dedicated kind of studies. There has been a departure from the traditional social security systems because now social security would be available in the market that may be purchased. However, even the development initiatives have also compelled the government to ensure various social security free of cost or against nominal charges or participation fees. At the first glance all those may look very attractive, however, their utility and real delivery of services required study. If financial institutions failed on delivery, making false, promises, and diverting the issues were some major issues in Bihar. People being cheated by all such false promises and there was no Redressal of grievances for years. People are not getting returns or adequate returns on their investments. Social security cannot be arranged through students and farmers

credit card schemes or loans. Going cash or cashless is not the real issue.

There was a lack of information on particular social security needs of different social groups. The traditional social security system in India has been affected by the process of feudalism, colonization, democratization, and globalization. To suit such transformation it would be needed to study the needs of social security and the manner they would be met. It would certainly require transformations in existing institutions of funding and management of social security in India.

Almost ninety percent of the working population in India had no any social security coverage until now. Particularly the people in the informal sector are not covered by any type of social security protection, i.e. either by a contribution based insurance scheme or by any social assistance scheme.

Amidst uncertainties, the first National Labour Commission have defined the unorganized workers as "the group of workers, who cannot be defined by definition but could be described as those who have not been able to organize in pursuit of a common objective because of constraints such as the casual nature of employment, ignorance and illiteracy, small size of establishments with low capital investment, and scattered nature of establishment. Therefore, a large workforce engaged in agriculture, contract labour, including construction workers, casual labour, and labour employed in small-scale industry, handloom and power loom workers, beedi and cigar workers, employees in shops and establishments, sweepers and scavengers, workers in tanneries, domestic workers, and tribal labour may be identified as unorganized sector or informal workers. ,

While the increasing labour force in the country and the decrease in the organized labour in proportion to the growth is a major challenge to the social security systems in the country, the growth of the aged population, which is either dependent on the young or unemployed or working for food during the evening years of their life is another challenge to the social security systems in the country. The insecurity dimension of the unorganized sector workers ranges from poverty, casual employment, gender inequalities, old age and child labour, and non-enforceable labour laws (Madhavrao, 2002). There has been a great failure of the government in past in reducing poverty. There is a major in social sectors such as healthcare, promotion of rural households and livelihoods in the country. The public distribution system and other schemes such as aanganwadi centres don't deliver appropriately in many states. The conditions of energy, sanitation, and connectivity remained a major problem in many states of the country. Informal workers are heterogeneous and face several types of vulnerabilities and uncertainties in livelihoods. Even they also suffer due to labour market insecurity, including insufficient income and insecurity relating to shelter and basic amenities. In addition, insecurity relating to minimum basic needs like food and health are major challenges before social security in India. The state largely failed in contingencies related social protection needs and due to low levels of the income vast majority of informal workers are not able to resort to private provisioning needed for contingencies related social protection measures. The state sponsored promotional measures of social protection (PDS, education, employment and productivity enhancement) does not reach the overwhelming majority of workers (Arora, 2011). Most social security systems in developed countries are linked to wage

employment. In India the situation is entirely different as here is no universal social security system. India does not face the problem of exit rate from the workplace being higher than the replacement rate. Almost one eighth portion of the world aged population lived in India (Nilendu, 2012). Soon after independence the Director General of India's social security program had talked about looking forward to the time when "not only industrial workers, but everyone in this country will be protected against the social risks to which a man is ordinarily exposed in his life (Cohen, 1953). However, still such a large gap persisted in coverage, access, and adequacy of the social security. A well designed social security system for the workers in the unorganized sector would have helped help in improving productivity, contribute to the harmonious labour relations and thus to social and economic development. It would have also encouraged and propagated the social peace by reducing the frequency of industrial conflicts, increase the willingness to work, make it easier to meet delivery commitments and lead to improved quality product, a better investment climate and thereby enhancing the competitiveness of the economy (Vaish, 2001). The need for such highly subsidized programs arises in India because nearly ninety percent of workers in India earn their livelihood in the unorganized sector, which lacks social security schemes. The population in the unorganized sector, thus, remains most vulnerable to various unforeseen shocks which hinder poverty alleviation and inclusive growth (Singh, 2015).

Materials and Methods:

The methods of social security usually adjusted between the methods of demography, actuarial, behavioral risks, management, policy, programs and labour market studies. This particular research was involved with all those methods. The research methodology would be an amalgamation of the empiricism and qualitative methods of research including the case studies and interviews. The quantitative analysis would be also expedited that would involve with several statistical analysis and design of experiments.

Both the qualitative and quantitative approaches were used side by side, in combinations adapted to the context. The emphasis of contemporary research in social security mainly remained involved with policy research, legislative impact analysis, and providing technical assistance. More precisely various types of social security research involved with coverage studies, old age and survival studies, disability studies, supplemental security studies, and economic research.

The methodology was aimed to examine the experience of other countries throughout the world in providing economic security through universal social security arrangements. The methods of social security further adjusted between the methods of demography, actuarial, behavioral risks, management, policy, programs and labour market studies. This particular research would also involve with all those methods. The research methodology was also involved with empiricism and qualitative methods of research including the case studies and interviews.

Social security administrations usually seek improvements in their organizational and financial performance, with the objective of improving member services and benefits as well as by better extending social security to all. Innovations are needed to develop increasingly accessible and sustainable social protection systems which are socially inclusive and economically productive (ISSA, 2010). Data collected from

various social security registers of various departments of the government of India. Such information underwent statistical analyses and corroborated with other quantitative data from other secondary sources. Such data included household budget surveys and other regularly-collected data managed by national statistical offices or government ministries. Even data were retrieved from various market research agencies, policy think-tanks and development agencies that use opinion polls and participatory assessments

Results:

The social protection has been considered as a primary development priority, therefore, a well-designed and implemented social protection systems can powerfully shape countries, enhance human capital and productivity, eradicate poverty, reduce inequalities and contribute to building social peace (ILO, 2017). The focus is being shifted towards achieving universality in social security by 2030 (World Bank, 2012). The universal social protection includes adequate cash transfers for all who need it, especially: children; benefits/support for people of working age in case of maternity, disability, work injury or for those without jobs; and pensions for all older persons. This protection can be provided through social insurance, tax-funded social benefits, social assistance services, public works programs and other schemes guaranteeing basic income security. The universal social security in India has been advocated to prevent and reduce poverty, promote social inclusion and dignity of vulnerable populations. In addition, it also expected to promote economic growth, savings, political stability, social peace, and human rights (ILO, 2017). There may be varied methods and approached for achieving universality in social security. Every country needed to plan their strategies as per their own suitability and may implement such schemes either in contributory or non-contributory manner. It would need great reallocation of public expenditure, increasing tax revenues, reducing the debt burden, and end beneficiary making contributions. The ILO and the World Bank's shared objective are to increase the number of countries that can provide universal social protection, supporting countries to design and implement universal and sustainable social protection systems. As a part of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) countries of the world are being persuaded to initiate time bound actions. The social security systems of Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, and the Nordic countries are some good examples making some of the best countries to live in (The Guardian, 2017). Social security provisions usually varied in respective formal and informal sectors. Social security in informal sector. However, some of the provisions applied to both sectors, however arrangement any provisions may differ again. In general, social security arrangements included situations such as unemployment, sickness, disability, loss of livelihood or households, and old age is most relevant to informal sectors. Formal sector is more associated with issues such as work leave, sick leave, holidays, and pension or retirement benefits.

Social protection policies play a critical role in realizing the human right to social security for all, reducing poverty and inequality, and supporting inclusive growth – by boosting human capital and productivity, supporting domestic demand and facilitating structural transformation of national economies (ILO, 2014). Public social welfare systems have become more complex and varied over the years. The earliest systems focused on what we now think of the means tested assistance program (Thompson, 2000). The social problems in the economies in transition were stressed to

ensure a smooth economic transformation and the development of democracy, it was vital to strengthen social protection (ILO, 2001). Proposals put forward by the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) has called upon for Equality: Closing gaps, Opening trails; and Structural Change for Equality (Simone Cecchini, 2015). Several low- and middle-income countries are interested in extending their existing health insurance for specific groups to eventually cover their entire population (James, 2005) India was facing some common challenges with regard to ageing of their populations, urbanization, vulnerability to environmental shocks, increasing labour market fragmentation, growing income disparity, and the need to more fully exploit and leverage information and communications technologies (ICT) (International Social Security Association, 2013). The proponents of Universal Social Security coverage had since long argued that without universal coverage, inequities and problems would arise for both individual workers and the Social Security system (Social Security Administration, 1980). Women and men should have equal access to and responsibility over resources (Wood, 2016). Strategies to achieve universalism in emerging economies are as diverse as their respective historical experiences (UNRISD, 2012). There are four most often mentioned welfare states types, namely the Conservative, the Social democratic, the Liberal, and the Southern model, practicing different social security models (Caroline Dieckhoener, 2009). Non-contributory social security is increasingly attracting the attention of developing country policymakers and observers, not least as a mechanism to help address the perceived failure of contributory social security to reduce poverty in developing countries (Sigg, 2003). IFMR has analysed and characterized the nature of the challenges in the design and implementation of these schemes, and use this understanding as the basis to draw out lessons on the design and implementation of a Comprehensive Social Security Scheme in India (IFMR Finance Foundation, 2013). The size and social importance of the Social Security program will make this subject a central part of public finance in future years (Martin Feldstein, 2002). Lower-income countries not only sold but also can have social security systems that provide a basic package of health services to everybody, basic cash benefits to the elderly and families with children and social assistance to a proportion of the unemployed (International Labour Organization, 2008). In developing countries, extending social security coverage would require delinking social security benefits and labour market status; creating new institutions to cover currently excluded groups; financing these new programs through general taxation; improving tax collection; reducing the costs of formal-sector benefits; and increasing the costs of informal-sector benefits (Dethier, 2007). Conditional cash transfers, employment guarantees, social pensions and unemployment savings accounts along with other policy instruments have contributed to expanding the coverage of social protection in developing countries (Laiglesia, 2011). The National Social Security, Strategy (NSSS) of Bangladesh stated that the focus would be to help people move out of poverty (Planning Commission, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 2015).

Globalization has caused a situation whereby there is an increase in unemployment and inequality and it has increased the social security demands (Herzog, 2009). Acting on the sides of the globalization, the international developmental initiatives have talked about the good

governance and administrative reforms vital for economy (Ambati, 2007). The economy with cheap and low skilled workforce like India, China, and Brazil made economic progress in the initial phase of globalization, however skilled labour forces in those countries suffered due to unemployment and low wages. Even the elderly people needed social security was massively in India due to rise in average life expectancy (Keidanren, 2011). Adopting and implementing those social security provisions was though mandatory due to certain international development and globalization compulsions of agreements and protocols, however, it never restricted wise person to work without application of mind. However, despite globalization the answer of the social security problem required to be found at the national levels (Satya, 2013). The role of the state in India was though constructed in organized and formal sector, however that was still needed to be streamlined and enhanced in the unorganized and informal sectors (Mini, 2010). There has been certain perception that globalization, though favoring capitalism may suppress the concepts of the welfare state (Alberti, 2002). Even United Nations advocated major role of the government for developing and implementing policies to ensure that all people have adequate economic and social protection during unemployment, ill health, maternity, child rearing, widowhood, disability and old age (UN, 1995). The three pillar approach of the ILO and World Bank also constructed a major role of the government in providing safety nets, and social insurance (Singh, 2008). The social justice movements in India of different social groups could not be fulfilled without social security and globalization (International Labour Organization, 2011). The social security coverage in case of substantial reduction of earnings resulting from sickness, maternity, employment injury, unemployment, invalidity, old age and death, the provision of medical care; and the provision of subsidies for families with children was already protected through the Social Security (Minimum Standards) Convention, 1952. In India the social security schemes were available in the form of the Workmen's Compensation Act- 1923, Maternity Benefit Act- 1961, Gratuity Act - 1972, Employees' State Insurance Act - 1948 and Employees' Provident Fund and Miscellaneous Provisions Act - 1952. Notwithstanding the above schemes, there is a great challenge before the country in providing social security to the entire workforce (Silas, 2004). India did not have a universal social security system and almost 90 percent workforce working in agriculture, construction, and trade were not covered (Nilendu, 2012). One of the key global problems facing social security today is the fact that more than half of the world's population was excluded from any type of social security protection. They are covered neither by a contribution-based social insurance scheme, nor by tax-financed social benefits, while a significant additional proportion is covered for only a few contingencies (ILO, 2001).

All those social security challenges of financing, funds management, and universality in access and compensation can be better addressed at the levels of the respective societies. Indian societies were successful in ensuring protection and safety of the helpless, the aged, the blind, the cripple, lunatics, widows, orphans, and those suffering from diseases, and calamities, pregnant women, by giving them food, lodging, clothing and medicines according to their needs for more than one millennium (Damodar, 1952).

According to *Kautilya*, Social Security was both a private and state matter (Rajan, 1992). *Kautilya* maintained that the children, the old, the destitute, those suffering from adversity, childless women and the children of the destitute women should be protected at the state's cost.

India was also having specified provisions for the social security funding. *Sukranitisara*, a compilation of rules of *Rajadharma* and allied topics mentioned that 1/6th or 1/4th part of the wages of an employee should be deducted (Sarkar, 1975). The whole business of helping people in need was everybody's business mainly handled in a collective way (Shastri, 1996). The main duty of a king, as stressed in all the works was the protection and welfare of his subject (Jois, 1990). The king was strongly advised to take preventive measures against social evils (Sinha, 1976). The purpose of gift giving (*Dana*) was said to be threefold: as a magic religious function of propitiating the supernatural; a mutual conferring of status; and as a means of exchanging and redistributing economic wealth (Thapar, 1978). But gradually by the time of the later Vedic period, *Dana* not only became institutionalized, but it also acquired the characteristics of charity with religious ideology as a sanction behind it. Though the notion of exchange and redistribution remained central, the donor acquired merit (*Punya*) in return by donating tangible wealth (Thapar, 1978). The family income was distributed among all the members without any consideration of the individual (P. V. Kane, 1941). It provided the universal insurance against unemployment.

Guilds in India derived their income from the gifts of the king, the profits earned by the corporate undertakings of the individual members and the income by the levying of actuarial and other duties" (Pathak, 1981). Those guilds provided Social Security to their members in distress, diseased, blind and infirm, orphans and helpless women (B. Thirumalachar, 1942).

During the *Mauryan* period, employment was also provided to the agriculturists through public works such as constructing or repairing the forts and water tanks. People working on such projects were supplied with food. During natural emergencies like floods and famines, the king distributed food and grains freely to the needy people. Social security was ensured through the village officer (*Gopa*) or city officials (*Nagaraka* or *sthanika*). *Ashoka* developed a very comprehensive system of social welfare which included women's welfare, rehabilitation of prisoners, rural development, free medical care and provision of public utilities (Pathak, 1981). The Gupta Empire flourished in Bihar made serious efforts to restructure the existing agrarian economy by giving land grants to individuals, thereby encouraging the conversion of the wasteland (Thapar, 2003).

The Joint family system, the caste system and the village community continued to play a major role in providing the security. The traditional social institutions like the kinship, caste and the village community imparted mostly provisioned the social security (More, 1962). *Lord Metcalfe* aptly described the power and the strength of the villages in India all throughout the centuries (Kaye, 1885).

There were various provisions in Islamic traditions that may have worked as foundations for pension schemes such as *Zakat* or charity. *Zakat* is one of the major foundations of Islam. There was another provision of *Jizya*. The taxes collected is used for the welfare of poor, elderly, orphans, widows, and the disabled. During the sultanate period, sultan also took interest in promoting the

general welfare of the masses. However, during famines, revenue taxes were generally not collected. The food grains, stored in the royal granaries were distributed to the poor. Charity was emphasized during the sultanate rule also. Emperor Akbar introduced substantial reforms in the state grants for charitable purposes the power confers cash grants or revenue free land (*madad-i-mash*) was vested in the office of the Sadr-Us-Sudar. These grants were made in four categories of persons, scholars, ascetics, the weak and the poor, and the disabled persons.

Moreover, the new economic realities, particularly those caused by market forces, generated new vulnerabilities, which could not be addressed through traditional systems (Gilbert, 1976). In traditional Indian society, parental responsibility as a value of joint family system was of paramount importance in protecting all family members. Premature death of servants entitled their families an allowance equivalent to half of their salary (Bhattacharya 1970). Many social mechanisms also developed to protect the people from adversities. An example of such mechanisms was Shreni (guild) system prevailing during the fifth century B.C. until about the second century B.C. it provided decent livelihood to all its participants (Thaplyal 2001). *Chanakya* does not mention the provision of health and education as the duty of the State (Kannan, 2007). The social security could not be restricted to mere Kings and lords in ancient India and in fact several major social institutions and systems developed (Sharma, 1979).

Discussion:

The proposed research would be able to support existing social security administrations in their ongoing endeavours to improve organizational inputs, processes and outputs. A social security administrations need valuable information for statistical and actuarial analyses, especially if combined with other quantitative data from household budget surveys and other regularly-collected data managed by national statistical offices or government ministries. By joining forces with market research agencies, policy think-tanks and development agencies that use opinion polls and participatory assessments they can reach a better understanding of the drivers behind people's behavior as consumers, voters and as actors in society. It is most likely that it would promote efforts to realize wider access to social security, with an emphasis on improving social security policy outcomes. In turn, it seeks to play a role in better ensuring the financial, political and social sustainability of social security administrations and the programs. The research would be a means of informing the social security policy. Such research would be ultimately a great source of guidance for policy makers and social security administration. The social security administration would be needed to map the knowledge and expertise as it is important to establish ways of ensuring that the organization identifies the information it needs, obtains that information and feeds it back into organizational decision-making. The research would aim to generate information with respect to beneficiaries, benefits, finance, and administration.

As a substantial data gap and lack of information persisted in terms of social security needs of different social groups. Without understanding their needs how it would be appropriate to compensate them adequately. The respective roles of society, market, financial institutions, industries, and the government needed to be expedited.

The project is significant because of interests of informal sector workers are so far largely neglected by the government. Informal workers are just able to get some sort of social security arrangement such as insurance and pension for which they have to contribute. Any non-contributory, accessible, and sustainable social security arrangements has so far alluded non formal workers in India. Informal workers, both in India and other countries take the load of the formal economy and amidst globalization such loads have increased further. So far informal workers are not compensated at par with formal sector that is major inequality needed to be urgently patched. Different social groups have different problems and objectives therefore any social security must be catering to those respective problems and objectives.

The project has some great relevance for both India and other developing economies of the world. There is an unprecedented undercurrent in the social security sector, both at the national and international levels. The globalists, develop Mentalists, and social scientists have been engaged in identifying various strategies, funding opportunities, and sustenance as well possible effects of any such schemes on the market economy and labour productivity. In the contexts of India, which is a major developing economy of the world, any such issues needed to be studied in varied manner.

The project would come out with strategies and approaches needed to implement and sustain any universal social security in India. It would describe the respective roles of the government, industries, market, and the community. In addition, it would be presented the manner any such scheme can serve the interests of respective informal workers, society, industries, and market.

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